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Reform Measures and Effect of the Excellent Course "Design and Humanities-Contemporary Public Art" of Ideological and Political Theories Teaching in All Courses During the Epidemic Prevention and Control Period

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ABSTRACT

During the special period of fighting against the "Covid-19", this paper takes the construction of the excellent course "Design and Humanities-Contemporary Public Art" in Tianjin's Ideological and Political Theories Teaching in All Courses as an example, combined with the practice of the construction the methods of ideological and political teaching. The article focuses on reforms in the four aspects of teachers, courses, teaching evaluation and students' sense of gain, the new online teaching medium was fully utilized to extend the influence of ideological and political courses to professional courses and general courses, and remarkable results were achieved.

INTRODUCTION

At the beginning of 2020, the ravages of the Covid-19 were contained in China with the wise and decisive decision of the Party Central Committee, the brave dedication of medical staff and the joint efforts of the people of the whole country. Overcoming the difficulties together, the education sector cannot be absent. The Ministry of Education put forward the plan of "no suspension of classes" to ensure the implementation of the teaching plan. (1) In this special period, the ideological and political teaching cannot be ignored because of the change to online teaching. Instead, it should be used as a powerful tool to improve the quality of teaching and stabilize students' emotions. It should carry heavier responsibilities than ordinary courses, more intensive teaching reforms, and new developments in the application of educational information technology, and achieve more significant results in cultivating people with morality, as the actual practice of educators in fighting Covid-19.

The excellent course "Design and Humanities — Contemporary Public Art" of Tianjin's Ideological and Political Theories teaching in All Courses in the new era can timely adapt to and comprehensively promote the form of online teaching in a special period and flexibly adjust the modules of teaching evaluation. It is inseparable with the deep accumulation of the course itself and a solid foundation for online teaching. Therefore, before introducing the reform of the course during the special period, it is necessary to introduce the construction results achieved before and the scientific system design of the curriculum.

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Excellent course "Design and Humanities—Contemporary Public Art" of Tianjin's Ideological and Political Theories teaching in All Courses in the New Era

In 2018, in order to promote the spirit of the 19th National Congress of the Communist Party of China and the "Xi Jinping's new era of socialism with Chinese characteristics entering into textbooks, classrooms and students' minds", Tianjin City deeply explored the ideological and political connotation of each course, and decided to launch the excellent courses construction in the new era's "Ideological and Political Theories teaching in All Courses" reform in the city's colleges and universities, to ensure that each course is in the same direction as the ideological and political theory course. The course construction standards proposed in the "Construction plan for excellent courses in the new era's Ideological and Political Theories teaching in All Courses reform in Tianjin University (Draft for Comment)" is, excellent courses in Ideological and Political Theories teaching in All Courses reform must have the combined teaching goal of "value shaping, ability training, knowledge transfer". Ideological and political teachers are to impart professional ideological and political knowledge to students, while other professional teachers must combine the characteristics of their own courses to carry out ideological and political education deliberately, organically, and effectively to students during the teaching process. This is a new type of teaching concept called "Ideological and Political Theories teaching in All Courses ". The "Design Humanities—Contemporary Public Art Design" lectured by the author at Tianjin University was recommended by the university to participate in the selection. It was selected because the teaching objectives and the requirements of the plan are highly compatible, reflecting the distinctive ideological and political teaching results.

Guided by Xi Jinping's thoughts on socialism with Chinese characteristics in the new era, the course strictly follows the spirit of the report of the 19th National Congress of the Communist Party of China, gives full play to the course's advantages of "public art", and uses critical and dialectical methods to carry out in-depth analysis of art practices worldwide. In the new era, college students can more comprehensively and objectively analyze the development trends of art at home and abroad. At the same time, students are encouraged to inject Chinese spirit and Chinese style into public art design works, and pay attention to the environmental protection, timeliness, and interactivity of the works.

The course has achieved outstanding results during the construction period, and has successively won the first prize of the 2nd Excellent Alliance Young Teacher Teaching Innovation Competition and other awards. In the long-term ideological and political courses practice, the author has found out the systematic construction method of "the unity of knowledge and action, combination of practice and research; excellence and innovation, broad and subtle; seeking change in stability, taking certain control; achieving by hardship, encouragement in great harmony". Some progress has been made in the promotion of the construction method, and it was presented on behalf of the ideological and political teachers of the whole university at the closing meeting of the comprehensive reform work conference of "Three All-round Education and Five Education" in Tianjin University. Beginning in 2018, the instructor will give pre-job training demonstration courses for all new teachers of Tianjin University every year, introducing Ideological and Political Theories teaching in All Courses and online teaching. In 2019, the author was invited by the Academic Affairs Office of Tianjin University and the School of Marxism to give a lecture on "Experience Sharing of Ideological and Political Construction of Humanities and Social Sciences Courses" for teachers of the ideological and political demonstration courses of the whole university in the lecture hall. In the "Teaching Observation Month" in November 2019, two ideological and political demonstration courses were given to hundreds of teachers in the university and the newly recruited teachers of the Military Traffic Command Academy. In November 2019, the author went to Beijing Institute of Technology, Hebei Province Mixed Gold Class Seminar and other places to teach ideological and political construction of courses (See Figure 1, 2).

Figure 1 The author speaking at the Tianjin University Talent Training Work Conference of the teaching method of "knowledge, practice and research; excellent classroom teaching, innovative teaching means, wide range of teaching resources and cultivation of fine personality; steady in teaching direction, changing teaching content, open teaching evaluation and control teaching process; achieving results by hard learning process, innovative learning examples and sharing learning experience"

The following will introduce the effectiveness of reform effect during the epidemic prevention and control period based on four aspects: the key is the teachers, the foundation is the courses, the focus is on ideology and politics, and the effectiveness is on the students.

Role of Ideological and Political Teachers during the Epidemic Prevention and Control Period

The key to Ideological and Political Theories Teaching in All Courses lies in teachers. The author's teaching task during the epidemic period contains numerous courses, numerous students, numerous platforms, and the tight teaching time. The task is difficult, but the quality cannot be compromised. How to complete it requires teachers to have firm beliefs and give full play to their subjective initiative.

Effective Teaching

For many years, the author has been lecturing on the excellent ideological and political course "Design and Humanities — Public Art" in Tianjin University. This time, the author used the China University MOOC and SPOC platform for teaching, and nearly 200 students selected the course. At the same time, the author lectured on Tianjin University's ideological and political demonstration course "Global Public Art Frontiers" on the wisdom tree platform, and 3 classes selected the course, totaled more than 410 students. In 2020, the "New Engineering General Course"- "Five Thousand Years of Sculpture Road in China" will be opened, with more than 90 selected students. Besides, the author is responsible for teaching the second-year design course of the Environmental Design Department of the School of Architecture, two and a half days a week. As a university elective course, it is particularly difficult. The number of students is large and the teachers and students are unfamiliar. As an online and offline mixed course, the first face-to-face guidance Q&A, which was originally important, could not be implemented due to the epidemic, which puts an unexpected obstacle for the lecturer. To solve this problem, the first step is to change the way of think. The author understands the difficulties of students first getting involved in online learning. From the perspective of a first-time learner, the author worked overtime to prepare "Design and Humanities—Public Art" using China university MOOC and supporting tools. manual. In order to better communicate with students, each course uses multiple information release channels for online announcement, such as Yu Class, Zhidao, WeChat, MOOC classroom, and China University MOOC Platform. Special response in special period is to pay several times more effort than before. Especially in the first week of the guided learning class, we used MOOC Classroom to distribute multiple questionnaires throughout the whole process, collecting the

opinions of the students, and adjusting the learning methods to improve the teaching effect according to the feedback from the questionnaire on the mixed learning.

Taking on More Difficult Tasks

In addition to teaching, the author also serves as an online teaching quality assurance expert during the epidemic prevention and control period, responsible for the observing and teaching tracking tasks for multiple courses, helping teachers who are not familiar with online teaching and new teachers to improve teaching quality as soon as possible. The author also compiled his own experience in building new courses, including small steps and fast running in resource construction, eclectic communication between teachers and students, and clear and traceable teaching processes. The teaching methods were compiled into text and reported to the Academic Affairs Office, so as to provide useful references for colleagues.

In addition to the arduous teaching tasks, the author was also commissioned by the Academic Affairs Office of Tianjin University to squeeze time out of the tight preparation and teaching gaps to produce and launch postgraduate training courses on how to use the China University MOOC platform, to cultivate a new force of online teaching in this special period. From the moment of receiving the commission, the author took it as a task to record courses from his own personal experience, and strive to use concise language to improve the operation level of postgraduate teaching assistants, so that they can be a bridge between teachers and students. After receiving the entrustment, the course has been launched and published on the China University MOOC platform in just 45 hours after receiving the commission, which is a practical work done for effectively improving the quality of online teaching at Tianjin University during the epidemic.

Role of Ideological and Political Theories Teaching in All Courses during the Epidemic Prevention and Control Period

The foundation of Ideological and Political Theories Teaching in All Courses depends on the courses. Turning the crisis in a special period into an opportunity to improve the level of informatization of courses education will not only ensure the smooth development of teaching activities during the epidemic prevention and control period, but also lay a solid online foundation for long-term courses construction.

Giving Full Play to the Traditional Advantages of Online Teaching

The course itself has a solid foundation for online teaching. It was launched on the Chaoxing platform in 2017, and more than 70,000 students took the course nationwide. The lecturer has a wealth of online teaching experience. In addition to this course, the "Global Public Art Design Frontier" (Demonstration Course of Ideological and Political Teaching in All Courses in Tianjin University) and other courses have been built on platforms such as China University MOOC and Wisdom Tree, which have tens of thousands of students. Therefore, it can smoothly adapt to the situation where all the courses during the epidemic prevention and control period are changed to online teaching and achieve reform results.

Adjusting the Mixed Teaching Method in Time

The course "Design and Humanities—Contemporary Public Art" is built as a mixed online and offline course inside the university. The change to full online teaching in special periods poses new challenges to the previous teaching design. To this end, the author opened an on-campus SPOC on the authoritative platform China University MOOC, built the course framework in a short time, adopted the MOOC+SPOC learning method, and adopted innovative measures such as the "cloud evaluation" in the platform.

Providing Diversified Online Learning Resources

During the implementation of online teaching in colleges and universities across the country, a very prominent problem was exposed, that is, some courses moved traditional courses online directly, disregarding the characteristics of online teaching, which has affected the teaching effect. On the basis of long-term online teaching, "Design and Humanities" fully grasps the essence of online teaching, takes students' self-study as the main line, and provides a large number of carefully designed course resources, such as using the electronic version of special textbooks integrated with ideological and political teaching, such as Ecological Public Art and Plant Bionic Public Art, which have played a significant role in teaching. (See Figure 3)

Figure 2 Ecological Public Art, a special supporting teaching material for Ideological and Political Theories Teaching in All Courses combined with the construction of ecological civilization

Exploration and Promotion of the Content of Ideological and Political Theories Teaching in All Courses During the Epidemic Prevention and Control Period

How to integrate ideological and political content into the courses is the focus of the construction of Ideological and Political Theories Teaching in All Courses. Based on the goal of cultivating people by virtue, combined with the characteristics of the design course and its own rules, this course explored unique ways and methods of ideological and political integration, such as exploring cases and enhancing environmental awareness.

Exploring Vivid Ideological and Political Cases and Bringing Current Political Knowledge into the Classroom

In this course construction, the author paid attention to the many heroic deeds during the epidemic prevention and control period, and encouraged the students to shift the training themes such as ecological protection in previous years to the protection of wild animals. The reflection on smart devices was added to this unprecedented large-scale online teaching, actively guiding young students to pay attention to current affairs. The content of the course combines the "Community of a Shared Future for Mankind" proposed by General Secretary Xi, combined with the "big country responsibility" shown in the support of the "Belt and Road" countries and in the fight against the epidemic around the world, successfully inspiring students' enthusiasm for learning and enhancing the learning effect.

Using Design Topics to Improve Environmental Awareness and Promote Ecological Civilization

By the middle of this century, China will become a "prosperous, democratic, civilized, harmonious, and beautiful" socialist modern power. The report of the 19th National Congress of the Communist Party of China for the first time includes "beautiful" as one of the qualifiers of a modern socialist country. The word requires us to pay attention to the form of development while developing. General Secretary Xi Jinping once emphasized: "On the issue of ecological and environmental protection, we must respect the natural rules, otherwise we should be punished." The youth of the new era are the builders and

main force of society, whose awareness of environmental and ecological protection should be around by teachers. During the epidemic prevention and control period, it is also an opportunity for our society to rethink the relationship between man and nature. It is also a rare opportunity to promote the spirit of the party and raise students' environmental awareness. The course takes the construction of ecological civilization and animal protection as design topics, motivating students to actively search for materials, think deeply about the relationship between nature and economic development, and be able to use original ecological materials, technological progress, and other means to design ecological public art. Their environmental awareness is sublimated in this process.

Using Design Topics to Carry Forward Chinese Spirit and Embody Chinese Style and Features

Based on China's national conditions, this course adopts an attitude of *aufheben* to overseas theories, and guides students to integrate the Chinese spirit and the face of China into the practice of public art design. Because the report of the 19th National Congress of the Communist Party of China pointed out: "Persist in national action, cadres take the lead, starting from the family, starting from the baby. Deeply dig into the ideological concepts, humanistic spirit, and ethics contained in the excellent traditional Chinese culture, and inherit and innovate in accordance with the requirements of the times. Let Chinese culture show permanent charm and contemporary style." The course innovatively combines public art design with traditional culture. Through teaching methods such as the knowledge explanation of traditional Chinese cultural elements, the application of methods, and case analysis, the students' understanding and love of traditional culture will be enhanced. It is required to use the campus environment as a base and directly use the latest design methods to complete a public art conceptual design with the theme of promoting traditional culture. During the epidemic prevention and control period, special emphasis was placed on seizing the role of traditional Chinese cultural forces in fighting the epidemic. The theme should be positive and can be educationally significance.

Improvement of Student Learning Effectiveness during the Epidemic Prevention and Control Period

The effect of Ideological and Political Theories Teaching in All Courses lies in students. "In the new era, if ideological and political education is to be accepted by students, it must also make full use of new media and new technologies.... Use the expressions that college students like to carry out ideological and political education." (2) In special periods, the course mainly improves the learning effect by through improving students' online teaching environment, inspiring students to pay attention to hot social issues and encouraging students to participate in social practice.

Improving the Online Teaching Environment for Students

During special periods, all courses are taught online. Undergraduates and postgraduates spend a considerable amount of time facing the screen every day. In addition to lectures, most of the discussions and homework also need to be completed online. Research has shown that during this special period, the average total time of using electronic products for college students has reached 15.1 hours per day. (3) The burden of learning is heavy and the damage to eyesight is relatively large. How can we better protect the physical and mental health of college students while ensuring the teaching effect and the teaching calendar remain unchanged? We take this as one of the main goals pursued by Ideological and Political Theories Teaching in All Courses, because it focuses on the overall development of morality, intelligence, physique and beauty. Therefore, ensuring their physical condition should be the ideal effect we want to achieve. The course achieved that mainly by using various methods such as rationally arranging class hours, refining teaching content, and improving communication efficiency. In addition to classroom teaching tools such as China University MOOC and Zhi Dao, which are specially matched to the course, we also use WeChat groups and other methods to assist in communication according to the everyone's need of flexible use of time. This can ensure that college students use their eyes reasonably and reduce students' extracurricular learning burden. We also use audio and other forms to communicate with students appropriately. In the design of teaching content, instead of directly moving the traditional classroom online, we strictly follow the

characteristics of online teaching. The break time is flexibly set at every 25 to 30 minutes, and students are encouraged to get up and look far between classes for the care of their eyes, which will improve their physical health and achieve one of the main goals of educating people.

Inspiring Students to pay Attention to Hot Social Issues

As instructed by the Party Central Committee, the Covid-19 is both a major epidemic and a major examination. Therefore, teachers must be more responsible outside class. It is necessary to actively promote the party's policies through online platform channels such as class groups, convey the spirit of the central authority, and seize all time and space to promote positive energy. At the same time, the author has accepted many new media interviews with students to provide suggestions for students to better conduct online learning, and encourage classmates to join the Communist Party of China. Through the changes in teaching evaluation, students will be inspired to focus on hot social issues, which will promote teaching effects.

Encouraging Students to Participate in Social Practice

Paying attention to the application of what has been learned and focusing on matching the teaching content with the actual needs of the society have always been the characteristics of the construction of the "Design and Humanities-Public Art" curriculum. Many students' homework awarded and published, having become a case of social incentive mechanism promoting the success of teaching quality. During the epidemic prevention and control period, in order to better promote the righteousness of the society and strongly support the front-line personnel in the fight against the epidemic, the lecturer actively organized students to participate in public welfare works collection activity "China is better if you're better", the "New Power to Fight the Epidemic, Youth Have Responsibilities" organized by Phoenix.com, and mobilized students to participate in the "Call for Protagonists of Youth BANG Long Holiday Story" organized by Youth BANG, and encouraged them to create with the theme of "In the days outside campus, I'm...". The activities promote positive energy, effectively stimulate students' enthusiasm for learning and use their own brush and mouse to contribute to the country. (See Figure 4)

Figure 3 Praising "The Most Beautiful Retrograde"-homework of excellent course of Ideological and Political Theories Teaching in All Courses (Instructor: Wang He)

Conclusion

Ideological and political teaching in all courses is not only the responsibility of ideological and political teachers. As General Secretary Xi Jinping once pointed out: "All other courses must maintain a certain channel and plant a good field of responsibility, so that all kinds of courses and ideological and political theory courses should follow the same direction, creating synergistic effect." (4) Therefore, every professional and general course teacher who is committed to the construction of Ideological and Political Theories Teaching in All Courses has the obligation to conduct research based on his own practice. Based on this, the ideological and political teaching experience summary of this course carried out in a special period is derived from professional course teachers, combined with theory, and elucidated by their own practical experience. It is not entirely a systematic study of the ideological and political connotation of the curriculum, but it is in line with the current trend of studying Ideological and Political Theories Teaching in All Courses under the background of multidisciplinary research and promoting the innovative development of university morality. (5)

REFERENCES

- Han Xianzhou. (2019-11-11). "The key of ideological and political teaching in all courses lies in continuous learning", Tianjin Education News, (A3).
- Liu Shuhui. (2019-03-06). "How does the ideological and political work in colleges and universities 'adapt to the situation, advance with the times, and be new with the situation'", Tianjin Education News, (A3).
- Zhang Zhixin&Wang Lu. (2020-03-24). "How to protect children's physical and mental health with 'heavy' immersion in the e-learning environment", Guangming Daily, (A14).
- (2016-12-09). "Putting ideological and political work through the whole process of education and teaching to create a new situation in the development of China's higher education", People's Daily, (A1).
- Wan Li. (2019). "A review of the triple logic of 'Ideological and Political Theories Teaching in All Courses' research", Journal of Tianjin Academy of Educational Science, 2019(04): 36-41.